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A COMPARATIVE STUDY ON CLASSROOM MANAGEMENT TECHNIQUES AMONG GOVERNMENT AND PRIVATE SCHOOL TEACHERS

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Abstract

Classroom management is terms used by teachers to describe the process of make sure that classroom lessons run easily in spite of troublesome activities by students. Today, educators are anticipated to manifest a high degree of specialized competence, and therefore to be able to manage their classes in such a way that students originate the maximum benefit from their schooling. The study aimed to examine the comparative study on classroom management techniques among government and private school teachers. The investigator adopted survey method to study the classroom management techniques among government and private school teachers. For this study a sample of 300 school teachers from six various schools which are situated in Coimbatore district selected by the investigator using simple random sampling technique. The findings revealed that there is no impact of demographic variables were found both on emotional competency and class room management techniques among school teachers and there is no relationship was found between emotional competency and class room management techniques among school teachers.

Keywords: Classroom Management; Classroom Techniques; Education.

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1. Introduction

Teachers are manifestly expected to manage their classes in an extent way which enable the students to derive the maximum benefit and knowledge from their schooling. Besides students' general intelligence, home environment, motivation and socio –economic status, the teachers can make a great change in terms of student outcome or achievement and a substantial portion of that difference is attributable to their classroom management beliefs. The study discussed about the

type of approach which yields more success in the classroom such as discipline, interventionist, noninterventionist, or interactionalist fosters. The teachers' pay scales should be based on classroom management instead of teaching experience and educational degrees. The present study will be more helpful to analyze the teaching competency compared with the classroom management techniques with the sample of 300 teachers encompass of Government and Private School Teachers.

1.1. Objectives of the Study

There are two main types of objectives undertaken by the investigator in this study work.

1.1.1. General Objectives

- 1) To find out the classroom management techniques of Government and Private School Teachers.

1.1.2. Specific Objectives

- 1) To find out the level of classroom management techniques of Government School Teachers.
- 2) To find out the level of classroom management techniques of Private School Teachers.
- 3) To compare the classroom management techniques of Government and Private School Teachers.
- 4) To find out the impact of independent variables like sex, age, gender, locality, educational qualification, teaching experience and internet usage on classroom management techniques of the Government School Teachers.
- 5) To find out the impact of independent variables like sex, age, gender, locality, educational qualification, teaching experience and internet usage on classroom management techniques of the Private School Teachers.

2. Research Design

The investigator adopted survey method to study the classroom management techniques among government and private school teachers. For this study a sample of 300 Government and Private school teachers from six various schools in Coimbatore district were selected by the investigator using simple random sampling technique.

Table 1: Distribution of Samples based on Variables

S.NO	Category	Subgroups	Number	%	Total
1.	Age	Below 30 years	79	26.3%	300
		30 to 35 years	161	53.7%	
		Below 35 years	60	20%	
2.	Gender	Male	69	23%	300
		Female	231	77%	
3.	Medium of Teaching	Tamil	115	38.3%	300
		English	185	61.7%	

4.	Teaching Experience	Less than 5 years	157	52.3%	300
		5 to 15 years	120	40%	
		Above 15 years	23	7.7%	
5.	Locality	Urban	162	54%	300
		Rural	138	46%	
6.	Marital Status	Married	233	77.77%	300
		Unmarried	67	22.3%	
7.	Internet Usage	Frequently	12	4%	300
		Sometimes	74	24.7%	
		Never	214	71.3%	
8.	Type of School	Govt.	116	38.7%	300
		Private	184	61.3%	

Table 2: Scoring of each item

S.No	Technique	Question no.	Scoring				
			SA	A	N	D	SD
1.	Classroom Management Techniques	1 to 14	5	4	3	2	1

Table 3: Ranks assigned for the scores

Classroom Management Techniques	
Scores	Rank
14 to 32	Low
33 to 50	moderate
51 to 70	High

HYPOTHESIS 1:

There is no significant difference among the teachers in their classroom management techniques with respect to their Gender

Table 4: “t” value among the teachers in their class room management techniques with respect to their Gender

Gender	Number	Mean	S.D	t-value	Remarks
Male	69	2.1843	0.94	0.99	Not Significant
Female	231	2.1837	0.80		

The table 4 exhibits that the calculated value (0.99) is less than the table value of ‘t’ (1.98), the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference among the teachers in their class room management techniques with respect to their Gender.

HYPOTHESIS 2:

There is no significant difference among the teachers in their classroom management techniques with respect to their medium of teaching

Table 5: “t” value among the teachers in their class room management techniques with respect to their medium of teaching

Medium of Teaching	Number	Mean	S.D	t-value	Remarks
Tamil	115	2.183	0.851	0.997	Not Significant
English	185	2.184	0.814		

The table 5 exhibits that the calculated value (0.997) is less than the table value of ‘t’ (1.98), the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference among the teachers in their class room management techniques with respect to their medium of teaching.

HYPOTHESIS 3:

There is no significant difference among the teachers in their class room management techniques with respect to their Locality of the Schools

Table 6: “t” value among the teachers in their class room management techniques with respect to their Locality of the Schools

Locality	Number	Mean	S.D	t-value	Remarks
Urban	162	2.18	0.88	0.96	Not Significant
Rural	138	2.19	0.77		

The table 6 exhibits that the calculated value (0.96) is less than the table value of ‘t’ (1.98), the null hypothesis is accepted. It is inferred from the above table that there is no significant difference among the teachers in their class room management techniques with respect to their locality of the schools.

3. Conclusion

- 1) There is a difference in the class room management techniques of the selected school teachers.
- 2) There is no significant mean score difference in the class room management techniques between male and female School teachers.
- 3) There is no significant mean score difference in the class room management techniques of the selected School teachers based on their age, locality, type of school, teaching experience and marital status.
- 4) No impact of demographic variables were found both on emotional competency and class room management techniques among school teachers
- 5) No relationship was found between emotional competency and class room management techniques among school teachers

Based on the study, it is found that the class room management techniques are important for teachers in the field of education to attain the educational goals. Hence steps should be taken to develop the class room management techniques among school teachers.

The building of relationships between the teacher and students, between students as peers, and connecting the students to the larger community are an important aspect of the role of the teacher. Districts, States and even nations have begun to work toward the establishment and requirement of attention to the social and classroom

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